

1 Behavior of method Linear Regression to estimate bias and accuracies with correct and wrong
2 genetic evaluation models
3 Macedo
4 Bias in genetic or genomic predictions needs to be checked to avoid wrong selection decisions.
5 Existing methods require a large amount of progeny tested sires. A recent method called LR
6 based on comparison of “recent” and “old” predictions theoretically allows estimation of bias
7 and realized accuracies, but its behavior in realistic situations is unknown. The present study
8 tested by simulation the behavior of method LR under several situations, assuming correct and
9 wrong models of evaluation, for low and moderate heritabilities. We verified that the method
10 LR was capable to estimate bias and accuracies in the proposed scenarios.

11 METHOD LR TO ESTIMATE BIAS AND ACCURACIES

12 **Behavior of method Linear Regression to estimate bias and accuracies with correct and**
13 **wrong genetic evaluation models.**

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ABSTRACT

22 Bias in genetic evaluations has been a constant concern in animal genetics. The interest in this
23 topic has increased with genomic evaluations, since many studies have detected an
24 overestimation (bias) of estimated breeding values (EBVs). Detecting the existence of bias, and
25 the realized accuracy of predictions, is therefore of importance, yet difficult for small data sets
26 or breeds. In this study, we tested by simulation the recently presented method Linear
27 Regression (LR) for the estimation of bias, slope and accuracies of EBVs. Method LR computes
28 statistics based on the comparison of EBV from a dataset with old information (partial) with
29 EBVs from a dataset with early information (old+new, or whole), for the same individuals. The
30 method proposes an estimator for bias ($\widehat{\Delta}_p$), an estimator of slope (\widehat{b}_p) and three estimators
31 related to accuracies: ratio between accuracies ($\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$), the reliability in the partial dataset (\widehat{acc}_p^2)
32 and the ratio of reliabilities ($\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$). We simulated a dairy scheme for low (0.10) and moderate
33 (0.30) heritabilities. In both cases, we checked the estimators of the method for three scenarios:
34 (1) when the evaluation model is the same as the model used to simulate the data; (2) when the
35 evaluation model uses a wrong heritability; and (3) when the data includes an environmental
36 trend. For scenarios when the evaluation model was correct, the method was capable of
37 correctly estimate bias, slope and accuracies, with a better performance for high heritability (i.e.
38 $corr(b_p, \widehat{b}_p)$ was 0.45 for $h^2=0.10$ and 0.59 for $h^2=0.30$). In the case of the use of wrong
39 heritabilities in the evaluation model, the bias was correctly estimated in direction but not in
40 magnitude. In the same way, the magnitudes of bias and of slope were underestimated in
41 scenarios with environmental trend in data. In general, accuracies were well estimated in all
42 scenarios. The method LR is capable to check the bias and accuracies in all cases, if the
43 evaluation model is reasonably correct or robust and the estimations are more precise as the
44 information increases (e.g. high heritability). If the model uses a wrong heritability or there is
45 a hidden trend in the data, it is still possible to estimate the direction and existence of bias and
46 slope but not always of its magnitudes.

47 Key words: genetic evaluation, BLUP, bias, accuracy

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INTRODUCTION

50 The study of the bias in genetic evaluation is an important subject in livestock genetics. This
51 topic has become more relevant in the genomic era as several works showed differences
52 between the predicted genetic value of top young genomic bulls at genomic prediction and after
53 progeny results (Spelman et al., 2010; Sargolzaei et al., 2012).

54 The two most used statistics to analyze bias in selection schemes are: (1) $b_0 = \bar{u} - \bar{\hat{u}}$
55 (difference between averages of EBV and true breeding values (TBV)), associated to the genetic
56 gain and (2) $b_1 = \frac{cov(u, \hat{u})}{var(\hat{u})}$, (slope of the regression of TBV on EBV) related to the dispersion
57 of the EBVs. Values of $b_0 < 0$ overestimate and $b_0 > 0$ underestimate EBV. In a similar way,
58 values of $b_1 < 1$ represent an overdispersion of the EBVs, which results on overestimation of
59 selected animals. Both biases produce an variation in the expected genetic gain with important
60 implications at the moment of taking selection decisions (Boichard et al., 1995; Mäntysaari et
61 al., 2010). It is therefore important to evaluate these biases in each genetic evaluation.

62 Preliminary studies in dairy sheep French breeds had shown overestimation of genetic gain
63 ($b_0 > 0$) as well as overdispersion ($b_1 < 1$). An overdispersion of the genomic estimated breeding
64 values (GEBV) was found in Lacaune, with more impact in that traits under important selection
65 pressure. Also, in the same breed, a $b_0 > 0$ were observed (Astruc et al., 2014; Baloché et al.,
66 2014).

67 The origin of these biases is unknown and should not occur under standard assumptions of
68 animal breeding (Henderson, 1984). In pedigree-based predictions, several situations can
69 produce bias, as the use of wrong heritability (h^2) in genetic evaluations, selective reporting,

70 wrong modelling of the age effect, ill-defined contemporary group effect or the use of genetic
71 groups in pedigrees. In genomic predictions, wrong models can also generate bias.

72 Nowadays, the most used tool in animal breeding to benchmark genetic models and detect bias
73 is time truncation of data and prediction of “future” records or averages of records (DYD).
74 However, this is difficult to do in certain contexts. For instance in selection programs with small
75 number of sires with small number of daughters each or for traits with low heritability (Legarra
76 and Reverter, 2017). In the case of Pyrenean dairy sheep breeds, one of the problems for
77 checking is the existence of few sires, each with small progeny groups (Barillet et al., 2016).

78 In 2018, Legarra and Reverter presented the method LR (Linear Regression) based on the
79 comparison of EBVs obtained from a dataset with old records (partial dataset) and from a
80 dataset with old+new records (whole dataset). It does not require extremely accurate EBV or
81 pre-corrected phenotypes and can be used for any kind of traits such as maternal effects on
82 offspring. At the same time, VanRaden and O’Connell (2018) also proposed the use of changes
83 in GEBVs to validate published genomic reliabilities, although they did not address the
84 existence of bias *per se*.

85 The method was formally presented and applied to an example data set (Legarra and Reverter,
86 2018), but it was not verified in depth. In particular, it assumes that the heritability and the
87 evaluation model are the correct ones, but these assumptions are not always true. In fact, it is
88 of most interest to know if the method LR works *when the model is wrong*. In this work, we
89 analyzed by simulation the potential of method LR to estimate the bias, the slope, and
90 accuracies on different scenarios. First, when the evaluation model is the correct one. Second,
91 when the heritability used for genetic evaluations is not the true one. Finally, when there is an
92 environmental trend in the data that is not explicitly accounted for by the model. These two
93 cases may not be the most frequent nowadays (e.g. the combination of genomic and pedigree
94 information is prone to errors) but the objective was to have a general impression of the

95 goodness of the LR method. Only pedigree-based evaluations were considered, because the
96 objective of the work is to confirm the ability of method LR for verification, and given the
97 complexity of genomic predictions for the large data sets generated and the large number of
98 replicates.

99

100

MATERIALS AND METHODS

101 *Simulations*

102 We simulated a dairy cattle breeding scheme with partially overlapping generations, progeny
103 testing and selection. Only females were phenotyped with only one record each, because of
104 limitations of the simulation software. Two heritabilities ($h^2 = 0.10$ and 0.30) were simulated.
105 We used the QMSim v. 1.10 software program (Sargolzaei and Schenkel, 2009), and the main
106 parameters of the simulation are shown in Table 1. In each generation, 8% of born males and
107 40% of born females were selected for reproduction. All born females have a single
108 performance. The mating system seeks to minimize inbreeding (mating design = *minf* in
109 QMSim parameter file) (Sonesson and Meuwissen, 2000), achieving an average inbreeding, for
110 all generations, close to 0. Instead of using QMSim “internal” BLUP evaluations, genetic
111 evaluations were performed at the end of each generation using as external software blupf90
112 (Misztal et al., 2002). Then QMSim selects individuals with higher (external) EBVs to be
113 parents for the next generation. This scheme allowed us the flexibility required to explore
114 competing scenarios.

115

116 Place for Table 1

117

118 We considered three different strategies to evaluate the individuals in the population: (1) using
119 the same model that the one used in simulation, (2) using a wrong h^2 for evaluation and (3)
120 adding an environmental trend. In total eight scenarios were obtained (two using the correct
121 model to evaluate, four using a wrong h^2 and two using an environmental trend effect). In all
122 cases, true breeding values were simulated as the sum of QTL effects, sampled from a gamma
123 distribution. All simulations use a genetic variance of 1, which implies that units (e.g. of bias)
124 are in genetic standard deviations.

125 **Correct genetic model.** Phenotypes were simulated adding a residual deviate to TBV
126 with two heritabilities: h^2 of 0.10 (*scenario T10*) and 0.30 (*scenario T30*). These heritabilities
127 mimic, respectively, lowly heritable health trait (e.g. subclinical mastitis) and moderately
128 heritable production traits. The population was evaluated using the same model as the one used
129 to simulate the data, $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{1}\mu + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{e}$.

130 **Wrong heritability.** Phenotypes were simulated as above with the same two
131 heritabilities. However, the models used for genetic evaluation used wrong heritabilities. For
132 simulations performed with an h^2 of 0.1 we used h^2 of 0.05 (*scenario W05*) and 0.15 (*scenario*
133 *W15*) in the evaluation models, and for data simulated with an h^2 of 0.3 the models for
134 evaluation used h^2 of 0.25 (*scenario W25*) and 0.35 (*scenario W35*).

135 **Environmental trend.** Phenotypes were simulated as the sum of TBV, residual, and
136 environmental trend as follows. At each generation, an environmental trend was added of the
137 form $t * k$, where t is the generation number and k is equal to half the genetic progress per
138 generation. Then, at each generation, nine CG with no effect were simulated and the individuals
139 were assigned randomly to each one. In order to guarantee genetic connections, CG included
140 5000 individuals. The reason for this is that the number of daughters per male is low (~11) and
141 there is little overlap across generations. Hence, to ensure connectedness, large groups are

142 needed. Previous experimentation with 500 individuals provided very low connectivity, but
143 results were qualitatively similar (not shown). An example of phenotypic, genetic and
144 environmental trend is shown in Figure 1. In the genetic evaluation model, CG was included as
145 a fixed effect, $y_{ij} = CG_i + u_j + e_{ij}$. It is expected that the CG will capture the environmental
146 trend. A more sensible model (the “correct” one) would be a regression on time to account for
147 environmental trend, plus CG, $y_{ij} = t * k + CG_i + u_j + e_{ij}$. We simulated two heritabilities,
148 0.10 (*scenario ET10*) and 0.30 (*scenario ET30*).

149

150 Place for Figure 1

151

152 ***Data analysis***

153 For each scenario, 20 replicates were obtained with 10 generations each and the LR method
154 was applied starting in generation 5. After each generation there is a BLUP genetic evaluation
155 run by blupf90 (Misztal et al., 2002). Thus, for each replicate there are 10 BLUP genetic
156 evaluations. The method LR proceeds by comparing, only for individuals of interest (focal
157 individuals), EBVs with little information (partial) at genetic evaluation n and EBVs with more
158 information (whole) at genetic evaluation $n + 1$. Individuals of interest were males (~1800 in
159 each generation) with parent average information during genetic evaluation n , and performance
160 from daughters during genetic evaluation $n + 1$. In this manner, we have five comparisons per
161 replicate (5-6, 6-7, and so on until 9-10). For EBVs from each pair of partial-whole datasets,
162 we estimated the bias, slope and accuracies using the formulas shown below, and we compared
163 with true bias, slope and accuracies. These are obtained comparing the EBVs in genetic
164 evaluation n with TBVs.

165 **Estimators**

166 The LR method proposes estimators of bias (Δ), slope (b), ratios of accuracies (ρ) and
 167 accuracies (acc). For a deeper description of the statistics see Legarra and Reverter (2018). All
 168 the estimators can be used in multiple trait evaluations as well.

169 **Bias.** $\widehat{\Delta}_p = \widehat{u}_p - \widehat{u}_w$. Where \widehat{u}_p are the EBV based on partial dataset and \widehat{u}_w are the
 170 EBV based on whole dataset. This statistic estimates the true bias (Δ_p) between the EBV and
 171 the TBV, i.e., $\widehat{u}_p - \bar{u}$, where u represent the TBV. In absence of true bias, the expected value
 172 of $\widehat{\Delta}_p$ is zero.

173 **Slope.** $\widehat{b}_p = \frac{cov(\widehat{u}_w, \widehat{u}_p)}{var(\widehat{u}_p)}$. This is the slope of the regression of estimated breeding values
 174 with whole dataset (EBV_w) on estimated breeding values with partial dataset (EBV_p). This is
 175 an estimator of the true slope $b_p = \frac{cov(u, \widehat{u}_p)}{var(\widehat{u}_p)}$. This estimator is related to the dispersion of EBV
 176 and the expected value of $\widehat{b}_{w,p}$ in the absence of bias is 1. Values less than 1 indicate
 177 overdispersion of the EBV.

178 **Ratio of accuracies.** $\widehat{\rho}_{w,p} = \frac{cov(\widehat{u}_p, \widehat{u}_w)}{\sqrt{var(\widehat{u}_p)var(\widehat{u}_w)}}$. The expected value of this estimator is
 179 $\frac{acc_p}{acc_w}$, where acc_p is the true accuracy in the partial dataset and acc_w is the true accuracy in the
 180 whole dataset. Thus, $\frac{1}{\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}}$ is the relative increase of accuracy from partial to whole information.

181 E.g. if $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}$ is equal to 0.5, the addition of information doubled the accuracy.

182 **Accuracy in partial.** $\widehat{acc}_p^2 = \frac{cov(\widehat{u}_w, \widehat{u}_p)}{(1+\bar{F}-2\bar{f})\sigma_{g,\infty}^2}$. Where \bar{F} is the average inbreeding
 183 coefficient, $2\bar{f}$ is the average relationship between individuals, and $\sigma_{g,\infty}^2$ is the genetic variance
 184 at equilibrium in a population under selection (with true value known from simulation). This

185 statistic estimates the reliability (square of the accuracy) on partial dataset. In real data sets,
186 $\sigma_{g,\infty}^2$ can be estimated (Sorensen et al., 2001; Lehermeier et al. 2017).

187 **Ratio of reliabilities.** $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2 = \frac{cov(\widehat{u}_p, \widehat{u}_w)}{var(\widehat{u}_w)}$. This is a measure of the inverse increase in
188 reliabilities from partial to whole, with an expected value $E(\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2) = \frac{acc_p^2}{acc_w^2}$.

189

190 To check the capability of the estimators we report (a) means and standard deviation of true and
191 estimated values, (b) correlations between true and estimated values. The purpose of reporting
192 the means is to verify if the method LR is a consistent estimator e.g. of the slope (for instance
193 if true slope is 0.9 we want find an average of ~0.9, not of 0.7 or 1.1). The purpose of reporting
194 the correlations, is to verify the precision of method LR. For instance, if the true ratio of
195 accuracies is 0.5 we want the estimator to cluster near this value.

196

RESULTS

197 *Scenario 1 – Correct genetic model*

198 Figure 2 shows, across all replicates, true and estimated biases. As the model used in the genetic
199 evaluation was the same used to simulate the data, no bias is expected. Nevertheless, true
200 (small) bias was generated due to chance. For the two heritabilities the estimator was able to
201 indicate the true value of bias ($corr(\Delta_p, \widehat{\Delta}_p) = 0.59$ for T10; Figure 2, left). The best estimation
202 was in the higher heritability scenario ($corr(\Delta_p, \widehat{\Delta}_p) = 0.61$ for T30; Figure 2, right). In Figure
203 2, points of the same color belong to the same replicate and it can be seen that they do not
204 cluster together. In other words, comparisons within replicates can be seen as independent.

205 Similar results were observed (Figure 3) for the estimator of the slope of EBVs ($corr(b_p, \widehat{b}_p) =$
206 0.45 for T10 and $corr(b_p, \widehat{b}_p) = 0.59$ for T30). Thus, the true slope was more precisely
207 estimated when the heritability was high ($h^2=0.30$).

208

209 Place for Figure 2

210

211 Place for Figure 3

212

213 Place for Figure 4

214

215 Figure 4 shows $\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$ and \widehat{acc}_p^2 (estimators of the accuracy gain from partial to whole and
216 estimator of reliability in partial) versus true values from simulations ($\frac{acc_p}{acc_w}$ and acc_p^2
217 respectively). There is good agreement between estimators and true values (scenario T10:
218 $corr(\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}, \frac{acc_p}{acc_w}) = 0.54$ and $corr(\widehat{acc}_p^2, acc_p^2) = 0.45$; scenario T30: $corr(\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}, \frac{acc_p}{acc_w}) =$
219 0.62 and $corr(\widehat{acc}_p^2, acc_p^2) = 0.53$).

220 The estimator $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$ has a similar behavior than $\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$, e.g. $corr(\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}, \sqrt{\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2}) = 0.91$ for both
221 heritabilities, 0.10 and 0.30.

222 ***Scenario 2 - Wrong heritability in evaluation model***

223 When we used the wrong h^2 in the model for evaluation, the largest differences could be seen
224 in the estimation of bias (Figure 5 and Table 2). The use of a wrong heritability generates a

225 strong true bias. As for the detection of bias, the estimator was able to indicate the bias in the
226 right direction but the magnitude is underestimated, for instance, the real bias of scenario
227 W05 is ~0.10 but the estimated one is ~0.05. These differences are more pronounced for lower
228 h^2 .

229

230 Place for Figure 5

231

232 Place for Table 2

233

234 Place for Figure 6

235

236 In the case of the estimation of slope, Figure 6 shows that the use of too high heritability results
237 in true values of slope b_p less than one, as indicated by Reverter et al. (1994a), being the impact
238 more important for the scenario simulated with an heritability of 0.10 (mean b_p of 0.83 in
239 scenario W15 and 0.97 in scenario W35). Nevertheless, in all scenarios the slope could be
240 indicated (Figure 6) ($corr(b_p, \hat{b}_p)$) for scenarios W05=0.53, W15=0.44, W25=0.46 and
241 W35=0.46). Table 3 shows the results of the estimation of the accuracies. In general, it is
242 possible to estimate both the ratio of accuracies ($\frac{acc_p}{acc_w}$) and the squared accuracy (acc_p^2). Note
243 that the values of the squared accuracies in $\widehat{acc_p^2}$ are very small, and this is because these
244 animals have very little information when selected as candidates for selection: a phenotyped
245 dam and maybe a few phenotyped half-sibs.

246

247 Place for Table 3

248

249 It is possible to observe a particular behavior in scenario W05. For instance, it estimates a
250 wrong value of $\hat{\rho}_{w,p}$ and of $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$. A possible explanation could be that because of the use of
251 too low heritability, where sires EBVs have a very small contribution from daughter's
252 phenotypes and the EBVs in successive genetic evaluations tend to strongly resemble parent
253 average EBVs.

254 *Scenario 3 - Not fitting environmental trend*

255 Because the contemporary groups are large enough, they capture correctly the effect of the
256 environmental trend and there is almost no bias in the evaluations, only bias due to chance and
257 relatively small (~ 0.05 genetic standard deviation). Figure 7 shows that this bias can be
258 estimated ($corr(\Delta_p, \widehat{\Delta}_p)$ is 0.46 for scenario ET30, and 0.41 for scenario ET10) but its
259 estimated magnitude is too small. The same happens with the estimator of the slope (Figure 8),
260 whose direction is well estimated ($corr(b_p, \widehat{b}_p)$ equal to 0.52 for ET10 and 0.60 for ET30) but
261 whose magnitude is underestimated. Accuracies are in general well estimated (Table 4).

262

263 Place for Figure 7

264

265 Place for Figure 8

266

267 Place for Table 4.

268

DISCUSSION

269 Several reports showed some concern about the bias in young bulls with genomic predictions
270 (Spelman et al., 2010; Sargolzaei et al., 2012; Mikshowsky, 2018). Using different
271 methodologies, several studies had detected bias (Liu et al., 2016; Mikshowsky et al., 2017). In
272 addition, bias is a problem that continues to motivate studies in dairy sheep. In Pyrenees dairy
273 sheep breeds selection schemes some bias was found, ranging from 4.92 (Basco-Béarnaise) to
274 16.98 liters of milk (Manech Tête Rousse) with pedigree evaluations and slopes of 0.44
275 (Manech Tête Noire) to 0.95 (Basco-Béarnaise) (Legarra et al., 2014); which demonstrates that
276 in some dairy sheep breeds there might be bias in the genetic evaluations. However, these
277 studies relied on the use of pre-corrected data, and we were interested in the possibility of using
278 official genetic evaluations to quantify biases and accuracies.

279 Studies searching for methods to analyze bias in genetic evaluations are not new (Reverter et
280 al., 1994b; Boichard et al., 1995). Reverter et al. (1994b) presented three statistics related to
281 dispersion, accuracy and genetic gain, obtained from subsets of EBVs of successive
282 evaluations. Boichard et al. (1995) presented three methods to check bias in genetic evaluations.
283 For the first two methods, work with raw data is needed, but the last method is based on statistics
284 obtained from EBV obtained from different datasets. Following the same principles,
285 Mäntysaari et al. (2010) developed the Interbull validation test for genomic evaluations, using
286 genomic estimated breeding values (GEBV) from a reduced dataset and DYD (Daughter Yield
287 Deviations) from a full dataset. However, this needs access to the raw data sets and DYD are
288 not always computable or reliable, e.g. in sheep or swine. In addition, for traits that have been
289 genomically preselected, the estimated genetic trends and DYD using pedigree information
290 only are possibly biased (Sullivan, 2019). Yet these pedigree evaluations pass the Interbull test,
291 although they may not pass the Mendelian Sampling variance test (Tyriseva et al 2018, Sullivan,
292 2019). As method LR does not use DYDs, it should not suffer from biased DYDs.

293 Comparing successive EBVs is advantageous because there is no need to access the full data,
294 and also because it is very simple to execute. This is why comparing EBVs was proposed by
295 Reverter et al. (1994b), and Boichard et al. (1995). The genetic interpretation of this
296 comparison, according to Thompson (2001) is “Informally this statistic is asking the question
297 does the recent data change the prediction of early animals. In a sense this is looking
298 backwards”. The method LR is an extension of the ideas of Reverter et al. (1994b). Using
299 standard BLUP theory, Legarra and Reverter (2018) showed that, comparing “old” and “new”
300 EBVs, it is possible to infer biases and also accuracies at the population level. However, its
301 behavior in practice is unknown. In particular, method LR assumes that the model for genetic
302 evaluation is perfect. In this work, we verified by simulation that method LR is robust to
303 departures from the true model, which is very advantageous because analytical models are
304 always compromises that do not reflect well the state of nature. In several cases, we observed
305 that the bias was correctly estimated in direction but not in magnitude. This is because if
306 estimated EBVs are too much, or too little, regressed (e.g. due to a wrong model) the statistics
307 used are, therefore, scaled but the sign does not change.

308 The ultimate aim of method LR and that of this study is to detect reliably systematic biases in
309 the genetic evaluations that, if ignored, would hamper the genetic progress. For instance, the
310 over-dispersion of EBV results in choosing too many young animals and a slower genetic
311 progress. Overestimating the genetic progress for a trait may result in change of selection
312 objectives. This problem is not merely theoretical, for instance, Powell and Wiggans (1994),
313 describe a bias in the US national evaluation that generated overprediction of breeding values
314 of US bulls in France (Bonaiti and Barbat, 1993).

315 Efron (2004) showed that parametric and nonparametric (cross validation) prediction error
316 estimates are related and, when the model used for genetic evaluations is believable, the
317 estimation of error using parametric methods is more precise than nonparametric method.

318 Therefore, as an ancillary property, method LR can assist finding a “believable” model from
319 which statistics of interest (i.e. biases and accuracies) can be obtained parametrically.

320 CONCLUSIONS

321 Method LR is capable to estimate bias and accuracies if the model is reasonably correct or
322 robust, and its estimates of bias and accuracies are better as the information increases (e.g. when
323 the heritability of the trait is high). For wrong genetic models, in our case, if the heritability
324 used in genetic evaluations is wrong, or there are hidden trends in the data such as
325 environmental trend, it is still possible to estimate the bias. The direction of the bias will be
326 correctly pointed out but not its magnitude. In other hand, the estimators of slope and accuracies
327 are generally well estimated for all scenarios. Further research is warranted to use the method
328 LR with real data.

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413 Table 1. Main parameters used to simulate populations in QMSim software program

Parameter	Value
Replicates	20
Generations	10
Total animals in populations	~ 450,000
Phenotype	Only one measure in females
Mating system	Inbreeding control
Selection	higher EBV's (BLUP)
Number of chromosomes	30
Number of QTL per chromosome	333

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417 Table 2. Mean, standard deviation (SD) and correlation between estimated ($\widehat{\Delta}_p$) and true bias
418 (Δ_p) when the h^2 used in the evaluation model was wrong ¹

Scenario	Estimated Bias (SD)	True Bias (SD)	Correlation estimated-true values
W05	-0.030 (0.006)	-0.111 (0.015)	0.77
W15	0.035 (0.005)	0.091 (0.010)	0.36
W25	-0.027 (0.007)	-0.054 (0.012)	0.55
W35	0.032 (0.009)	0.050 (0.014)	0.63

419 ¹Scenarios: W05= true h^2 0.10, used h^2 0.05; W15= true h^2 0.10, used h^2 0.15; W25= true h^2
420 0.30, used h^2 0.25 and W35= true h^2 0.30, used h^2 0.35

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422 Table 3. Mean, standard deviation (SD), and correlation between estimators ($\hat{\rho}_{w,p}$, \widehat{acc}_p^2 , $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$)
 423 and true values of accuracies ($\frac{acc_p}{acc_w}$, acc_p^2 , $\frac{acc_p^2}{acc_w^2}$, respectively) when the h^2 used in the
 424 evaluation model was wrong ¹

Estimator	Scenario	Estimated value (SD)	True value (SD)	Correlation estimated-true
$\hat{\rho}_{w,p}$	W05	0.587 (0.043)	0.366 (0.074)	0.41
	W15	0.305 (0.028)	0.360 (0.057)	0.43
	W25	0.371 (0.027)	0.340 (0.043)	0.50
	W35	0.319 (0.022)	0.349 (0.036)	0.45
\widehat{acc}_p^2	W05	0.020 (0.004)	0.018(0.008)	0.32
	W15	0.025 (0.003)	0.018 (0.006)	0.48
	W25	0.030 (0.004)	0.033 (0.009)	0.45
	W35	0.036 (0.003)	0.035 (0.008)	0.44
$\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$	W05	0.319 (0.051)	0.139 (0.055)	0.28
	W15	0.100 (0.011)	0.133 (0.042)	0.40
	W25	0.135 (0.014)	0.118 (0.030)	0.43
	W35	0.104 (0.008)	0.123 (0.025)	0.48

425 ¹ See note in Table 2

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428 Table 4. Mean, standard deviation (SD) and correlation between estimated ($\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$, \widehat{acc}_p^2 , $\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$)
 429 and true values of accuracies ($\frac{acc_p}{acc_w}$, acc_p^2 , $\frac{acc_p^2}{acc_w^2}$, respectively) when an environmental effect
 430 was simulated ¹

Estimator	Scenario	Estimated value (SD)	True value (SD)	Correlation estimated – true
$\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$	ET10	0.377 (0.031)	0.374 (0.061)	0.53
	ET30	0.337 (0.024)	0.338 (0.042)	0.59
\widehat{acc}_p^2	ET10	0.020 (0.003)	0.020 (0.007)	0.39
	ET30	0.032 (0.003)	0.033 (0.009)	0.58
$\widehat{\rho}_{p,w}^2$	ET10	0.143 (0.016)	0.144 (0.046)	0.42
	ET30	0.114 (0.011)	0.116 (0.028)	0.57

431 ¹Scenarios: ET10= h² 0.10; ET30=h² 0.30.

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435 Figure 1

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467 Figure 1. Phenotypic, genetic and environmental trend corresponding to the first replicate for
468 the scenario ET30 (environmental trend, $h^2 = 0.30$).

469

470 Figure 2. Estimated bias ($\widehat{\Delta}_p$) versus true bias (Δ_p) (scenarios T10: $h^2=0.10$ and T30:
471 $h^2=0.30$). Different colors are used for each replicate.

472

473 Figure 3. Estimated slope (\widehat{b}_p) versus true slope (b_p) (scenarios T10: $h^2=0.10$ and T30:
474 $h^2=0.30$)

475

476 Figure 4. Estimators of accuracies (scenarios T10: $h^2=0.10$ and T30: $h^2=0.30$). (a) Estimators
477 of the inverse of relative gain in accuracy from partial to whole sets ($\widehat{\rho}_{w,p}$) versus the ratio
478 between the accuracy with partial over the accuracy with whole (acc_p/acc_w) and (b) the
479 estimator of reliability on partial (\widehat{acc}_p^2) versus the true reliability on partial (acc_p^2).

480

481 Figure 5. Estimated ($\widehat{\Delta}_p$) versus True (Δ) bias when the evaluation model used a wrong
482 heritability (simulation performed with $h^2=0.10$ and evaluation model used $h^2=0.05$ (W05)
483 and $h^2=0.15$ (W15) and simulation performed with $h^2=0.30$ and evaluation model used
484 $h^2=0.25$ (W25) and $h^2=0.35$ (W35)). Scenarios T10 and T30 (when the h^2 used in the
485 evaluation model was the correct) were included for comparison purposes.

486

487 Figure 6. Estimated (\widehat{b}_p) versus True (b_p) slope when the evaluation model used a wrong
488 heritability (simulation performed with $h^2=0.10$ and evaluation model use $h^2=0.05$ (W05) and

489 $h^2=0.15$ (W15) and simulation performed with $h^2=0.30$ and evaluation model used $h^2=0.25$
490 (W25) and $h^2=0.35$ (W35)). Scenarios T10 and T30 (when the h^2 used in the evaluation model
491 was the correct) were included for comparison purposes.

492

493 Figure 7. Estimated bias ($\widehat{\Delta}_p$) versus true bias (Δ_p), when an environment trend effect was
494 simulated (scenarios ET10 $h^2=0.10$ and ET30: $h^2=0.30$).

495

496 Figure 8. Estimated slope (\widehat{b}_p) versus true slope (b_p) when an environment trend effect was
497 simulated (scenarios ET10: $h^2=0.10$ and ET30: $h^2=0.30$).